

The Influence of Organizational Commitment, Competency, Work Motivation and Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction and Its Impact on The Performance of Aceh Mineral Resources Energy Staff

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the effect of organizational commitment, competence, work motivation and organizational culture on job satisfaction and its impact on the performance of employees of the Aceh Office of Energy and Mineral Resources. The sample in this study was taken using a data collection method called the saturated sampling technique (census). The number of samples used was 117 respondents. Primary data collection is done by distributing questionnaires. The data analysis technique used in this study is The Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) from the AMOS statistical software package for hypothesis testing. The results showed that descriptively organizational commitment, competence, work motivation, organizational culture, job satisfaction and employee performance had gone well. Then the test results directly show that: 1) organizational commitment does not have a significant effect on job satisfaction, 2) competence has a significant effect on job satisfaction, 3) work motivation does not have a significant effect on job satisfaction, 4) organizational culture has a significant effect on job satisfaction, 5) job satisfaction has no significant effect on performance employees, 6) organizational commitment has a significant effect on employee performance, 7) competence does not have a significant effect on employee performance, 8) work motivation does not have a significant effect on employee performance, 9) Organizational culture has a significant effect on the performance of Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources staff. Then the results of this study found that the results of indirect testing of competence had a significant effect on employee performance through job satisfaction at the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources (partially mediator).

BACKGROUND

The rapidly changing community environment as a result of globalization has made public awareness to demand freedom, openness, independence and attention to their rights being open. The community seemed no longer afraid to criticize and even protest any government policy that did not favor the people (Rahmawati *et. al.*, 2011). Such a situation requires the government to immediately make various efforts to improve the performance of public organizations by making various efforts, one of which is by improving the performance of employees of government agencies.

The Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources as a government agency is also expected to be able to improve the performance of its employees, this is due to the performance of these agencies which are highly dependent on the performance of employees or human resources in this case the Civil Servants (PNS) who work at the agency. Agency employees are the main resource in supporting the agency's overall operational activities. So that the achievement of organizational goals is only possible because of the efforts of employees found in the organization. This means that there is a unidirectional relationship between employee performance and the performance of the agency where the employee works. If the employee's performance is good, then it is likely that the agency's performance is also good (Sedarmayanti, 2014). If the employee's performance is good, then it is likely that the organization's performance will also be good.

The success of the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources in carrying out its operational activities in providing services to the community is inseparable from the support of all employees of the agency. The better the performance of employees, the better will be the performance of the Department of Energy and Mineral Resources in Aceh. But in reality based on observations on 30 employees of the agency, it is known that employees of the Aceh Office of Energy Resources have different performance from each other. A real indication of differences in performance can be seen from the ability

to complete work. Some employees can complete their work in a timely manner, some even able to complete the work before the time limit for work ends. Conversely there were also employees who were unable to complete their work on time. Those who belong to this group certainly include employees with low performance.

Indications of differences in the performance of agency employees are also seen from the ability of cooperation in the work team. As employees of government agencies the ability to cooperate among fellow employees in completing tasks assigned to each field of work greatly determines the success of the agency in carrying out its duties and functions. Therefore, every employee is required to be able to work well together. The fact shows, employees of these agencies have different cooperative abilities. Some employees have good cooperation skills so they can work together in completing tasks that have been charged. Conversely there are still employees with poor cooperation skills. Those who belong to this group prefer to carry out work independently without having to work with other people even though the work is the responsibility of the team in a particular field of work.

The phenomenon related to some employee performance indicators as described above, is based on the results of preliminary observations on 30 respondents who worked at the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources. Quantitatively and referring to the results of the performance assessment of civil servants in general, there are differences in the performance of employees of the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources can also be seen from the Employee Performance Target (EPT), which indicates that most employees of these agencies have values below 85 especially for items service orientation, integrity, commitment, discipline, cooperation, and leadership. This indicates that most employees of the agency were considered to have relatively low performance appraisal results. Moreover, employees with the results of work performance assessment 95 (excellent work performance category) are only a small part of the total number of employees.

Table 1. Employee Performance Target (EPT) in 2016

No	Type of Assessment	Frequency of Employees Based on Employee Performance Goals				Total
		< 85	85-90	91-95	≥ 95	
1	Service Orientation	72	29	16	-	117
2	Integrity	95	19	3	-	117
3	Commitment	99	14	4	-	117
4	Discipline	97	20	-	-	117
5	Cooperation	99	18	-	-	117
6	Leadership	110	7	-	-	117

The observations and experiences of researchers while working at the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources also found that the commitment or sense of attachment and competence of the agency's employees were relatively different from each other. The difference in commitment or sense of attachment of employees to these agencies can be seen from their willingness to be serious in completing the tasks charged. Not only that, until now there are still among the employees who want to move to other agencies other than the Aceh Department of Energy Resources. this indicates that the commitment or sense of attachment of the employee is very low.

Differences in competency can be seen from the skills of employees in utilizing work equipment used. Some employees are quite skilled in utilizing the work equipment provided, such as the use of computers for example, so that the ability to complete work is also getting better. On the contrary, there are still employees of the agency who have poor skills so that they have a negative impact on their ability to complete work.

In addition to the differences in performance and competencies as explained above, the motivation of work of employees and their assessment of the organizational culture of the Department of Energy and Mineral Resources in Aceh are also relatively different. The difference in work motivation among employees can be seen from their ability to comply with the rules that apply in the workplace. The presence of some employees who are late for work and leave the workspace during office hours is one indicator of the problem in the employee's motivation to work. For more details, the results of these observations can be seen in the table below:

Table 2. The Percentage of Employees in the Office of Staff of the Energy and Mineral Resources Department in Aceh for 10 Working Days in November 2017

Day	The Existence of Indoor Employees
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	Presence	At 8.30 to 12.00 WIB	% Indoor	At 14.00 to 16.00 WIB	% Indoor
Monday	110	70	63.63	47	42.72
Tuesday	103	62	60.19	42	40.77
Wednesday	108	60	55.56	39	36.11
Thursday	101	59	58.41	41	40.59
Friday	96	47	48.95	33	34.37
Monday	112	76	67.85	44	39.28
Tuesday	107	56	52.33	40	37.38
Wednesday	91	50	54.94	38	41.75
Thursday	104	52	50.00	45	43.27
Friday	97	41	43.29	32	32.99
Average in the Workspace			55.51		38.92

Source: Primary Data, 2018

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the average percentage of employees in the workspace from 8.30 WIB to 12.00 WIB is only 55.51% and only 38.92% of the employees are in the office at 14.00 WIB until 16.00 WIB of the total number of employees present at the 10 working days.

Furthermore, from the above phenomena it can be concluded that the amount of work that could have been completed on time but could not be implemented, because the desire of employees to be in the office or work motivation to complete the work was relatively less impacted on the decline in performance for some employees at the Department of Energy and Mineral Resources Aceh. This can be seen from the number of employees who ignore their main duties and functions as well as their responsibilities optimally.

This is indicated by the realization of the achievement of work targets that each year do not reach the target as set out in the Strategic Plan so that it is not in accordance with the BID (Budget Implementing Document). As an example of the main tasks in realizing programs related to budgeting, supervision that has a strategic impact on the people of Aceh and other impacts on development and community welfare is still not in accordance with the expectations and plans agreed upon.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Employee Performance

According to Pasolong (2014: 176) employee performance is all the results of all forms of actions and policies in a series of work ventures in a certain period of time in order to achieve a goal. Whereas according to Mangkunegara (2015: 67) said that employee performance is the work result in the quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him.

2. Job Satisfaction

According to Robbins (2013) job satisfaction is a general attitude towards one's work, the difference between the number of people they believe they should receive. Whereas Rivai (2014) states, job satisfaction is an evaluation that describes a person with a feeling of being happy or unhappy, satisfied or not satisfied at work.

3. Organizational Commitment

Malthis and Jackson (2012) define, "*organizational commitment is the degree to which employees believe in and accept organizational goals and desire to remain with the organization*". Furthermore, Mowday as quoted by Sangadji and Sopiah (2013) states that organizational commitment is an important behavioral dimension that can be used to assess the tendency of employees to stay as members of the organization.

4. Competency

According to Sedarmayanti (2014: 125) states that competence includes a variety of technical and non-technical factors, personality and behavior, soft skills and hard skills, then is widely used as an aspect that is considered by many companies to recruit employees into the organization.

5. Work Motivation

Sedarmayanti (2014: 233) states, motivation is the willingness to issue high efforts towards organizational goals that are controlled by the ability of the effort to meet individual needs. Whereas

Segal (2010: 26) states "work motivation is seen as a willingness to use desire to move and guide towards goals, help take initiative and act very effectively and endure failure and frustration".

6. Organizational Culture

Organizational culture is a system of shared meanings adopted by members who distinguish the organization from other organizations (Robbins, 2013). Then according to Davis in Moeheriono (2014: 336) interpreting organizational culture as a pattern of beliefs and values of the organization that are understood, imbued, and practiced by organizations so that the pattern gives its own meaning and becomes the basis for the rules of behavior in the organization.

RESEARCH MODEL

The model in this study illustrates the relationship of independent variables, namely Organizational Commitment (X1), Competence (X2), Work Motivation (X3), Organizational Culture (X4) to dependent variables namely Employee Performance (Z) with Job Satisfaction (Y) as a variable mediation. The following research models developed in this study:

Figure 1. SEM model developed in this study (2018)

RESEARCH METHOD

1 Samples and Population

This research was conducted at the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources. Whereas the population in this study were all employees of the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources, which amounted to 117 people who were sampled in this study using Saturated Sampling Techniques.

2 Data Analysis Equipment

The data analysis technique used in this study is The Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) from the AMOS statistical software package for hypothesis testing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Analysis

Based on the results of observations on organizational commitment to obtain an average value of 3.41, meaning that organizational commitment variables are perceived positively by respondents so that it can be identified that the organizational commitment to the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources is good. For the competency variable as a whole the average score is 3.55. This means that respondents have a positive perception of the competency variable or it can be identified that the competency variable in the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources is good. Employee motivation is good, this can be seen from the overall average value of the work motivation variable of 3.31. Then as a whole the average value on the variable is 3.51, it means that the organizational culture in the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources is good. Furthermore, for the overall average score on the variable job satisfaction of 3.31, this explains that the variable job satisfaction in the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources has been going well, and finally for the variable employee performance has also been good this can be seen from the average value in variable employee performance of 3.81.

Data analysis

1 Structural Equation Modeling (SEM): The First Stage Approach with the Measurement Model.

All constructs (organizational commitment, competence, work motivation, organizational culture, job satisfaction and employee performance) will be combined in the measurement model stage. The results of the measurement model analysis at the initial stage show the following results:

Picture 2. Measurement Model Analysis

Based on the measurement model shows the results that are still less fit, thus must be re-specified (Hair et al. 2006). X^2 results with 117 respondents = 2245,349, GFI = 0,586, TLI = 0,558, CFI = 0,586, and RMSEA = 0,120 only able to produce marginal fit conditions, therefore, need to be re-specified. In detail there are indicators that have a value of large MI > 10,000. The final results of the measurement model can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 3. Re-specified Analysis Model

The results of the above analysis indicate that the Chi-square value = 296.990 ($p < .000$) with $X^2/df = 1.362$. GFI value is 0.828, TLI is 0.894 and CFI is 0.909 > 0.90 shows the results of good fit. The RMSEA value of 0.056 has shown a satisfactory value, which is between 0.05 - 0.08 (requirements).

2. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM): Step-Two Approach with a Structural Approach

Based on the data that has been validated according to the measurement equation model through the first step approach, further analysis can be done with the second step approach or structural equation model. In the previous section, the results of the measurement model have achieved acceptable fit index results, with parameters that are statistically significant and significant.

Apart from the above, in the phase of this measurement model, the unidimensionality and reliability of all variables have been tested to reach acceptable levels. Furthermore, the structural in measurement model tests predictive validity or hypothesis testing. The output in Figure 4.5 shows that the structural equation model is fit and satisfactory for data with samples $X^2 (117) = 296.990$ at $p < .001$; $X^2/df = 1.362$, GFI = 0.828, TLI = 0.894, CFI = 0.909 and RMSEA = 0.056. This output also shows that all loading factors in the model are significant at $p < .001$. As explained earlier, the goodness of fit statistics (ie X^2) must display $p > .05$ to get a good and fit model. As shown in the following picture:

Figure 4. Analysis of Structural Equation Modeling

Hypothesis Test Results

1 Testing Hypotheses with Direct Effects

Hypothesis testing is based on the value of Critical Ratio (CR) and the Probability (P) value of the data, with the constraints implied, namely the value of CR > 1.96 and P < 0.05. The following table results of research hypothesis testing that has been obtained based on data processing:

Table 3. Relationship Between Construction

			Esti mate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
Job Satisfaction	←	Organizational Commitment	-.019	.063	-.303	.762	par_8
Job Satisfaction	←	Competence	.642	.081	7.934	***	par_9
Job Satisfaction	←	Work Motivation	.004	.072	.052	.959	par_10
Job Satisfaction	←	Organizational Culture	.333	.087	3.815	***	par_11
Employee Performance	←	Job Satisfaction	-.075	.193	-.388	.698	par_1
Employee Performance	←	Organizational Commitment	.708	.083	8.525	***	par_12
Employee Performance	←	Competence	-.116	.168	-.691	.490	par_13
Employee Performance	←	Work Motivation	.126	.098	1.278	.201	par_14
Employee Performance	←	Organizational Culture	.285	.148	1.919	.055	par_15

Source: Results of Data Analysis, 2019

Based on the table of direct effect test results above, can be obtained:

- 1) Hypothesis 2 is accepted, Organizational Commitment has a direct, positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of employees of the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources.
- 2) Hypothesis 3 is rejected, Competence does not affect the job satisfaction of employees of the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources.
- 3) Hypothesis 4 is rejected, work motivation does not affect the job satisfaction of employees of the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources.
- 4) Hypothesis 5 is accepted, organizational culture has a direct, positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of employees of the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources.
- 5) Hypothesis 6 is rejected, Job Satisfaction does not affect the performance of employees of the Aceh Office of Energy and Mineral Resources.
- 6) Hypothesis 7 is accepted, Organizational Commitment has a direct, positive and significant effect on the performance of employees of the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources.
- 7) Hypothesis 8 is rejected, competency does not affect the performance of employees of the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources.
- 8) Hypothesis 9 is rejected, work motivation does not affect the performance of employees of the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources.
- 9) Hypothesis 10 is accepted, organizational culture has a direct, positive and significant effect on the performance of employees of the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources.

2 Testing Hypotheses With Indirect Effects

As mentioned earlier, this study also has mediating variables, namely job satisfaction, so there is a need to test the effects of mediation as suggested by Kelloway (1995). This process is also carried out through structural equation models where structural equation models are seen as superior models in mediation testing as explained by Anderson & Gerbing (1988) and Kelloway (1995)

Table 4. Indirect Effects

Construct	Organizational Culture	Work Motivation	Competence	Organizational Commitment
Job satisfaction	,000	,000	,000	,000
Employee Performance	-,030	,000	-,058	,002

Source: Output from the Standardized Indirect Effect

The following are the results of testing mediation effects:

- 1) Hypothesis 11 is rejected, organizational commitment does not have a significant effect on employee performance through job satisfaction.
- 2) Hypothesis 12 is accepted, competence has a significant effect on employee performance through job satisfaction. Where the role of job satisfaction in this case is partially mediator based on assumptions suggested by Kelloway (1995).
- 3) Hypothesis 13 is rejected, work motivation does not have a significant effect on employee performance through job satisfaction.
- 4) Hypothesis 14 is rejected, work motivation does not have a significant effect on employee performance through job satisfaction.

Interpretation of Proof of the Hypothesis

The following session will explain and interpret the role of each variable in the model that has been built in this study.

1) The Role of Variable Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment variable, based on regression analysis proved to have a positive and significant relationship with job satisfaction (H2). This condition implies that the better organizational commitment of employees of the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources turned out to have an effect on the increasing job satisfaction of employees. Furthermore, if it is associated with employee performance, the results of this analysis also show that there is a positive and significant relationship between organizational commitment and employee performance (H7). This means that increasing organizational commitment will have a positive impact on improving employee performance at the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources.

Based on the description above, it can be interpreted that there is a role for the variable organizational commitment in this research model in the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources in increasing job satisfaction and employee performance.

2) The Role of Competency Variables

Competency variables, based on regression analysis, proved to have a positive and significant relationship with job satisfaction (H3). This condition means that the better the competencies possessed by the employees, the more job satisfaction for the employees of the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources. Furthermore, if it is associated with employee performance, the results of the analysis show that there is no positive and significant relationship between competence and employee performance (H8). This means that improving good competence will not have a positive impact on improving employee performance at the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources.

Based on the description above, it can be interpreted that there is a role for competency variables in this research model in the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources in increasing employee job satisfaction.

3) The Role of Work Motivation Variables

Work motivation variable, based on regression analysis, proved not to have a positive and significant relationship with job satisfaction (H4). This condition means that the better work motivation of the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources employees does not affect the job satisfaction of the employees. Furthermore, if it is associated with employee performance, the results of the analysis also show that there is no positive and significant relationship between work motivation and employee performance (H9). This means that the high work motivation of employees does not have an impact on improving employee performance at the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources.

Based on the description above, it can be interpreted that there is no role for work motivation variables in this research model in the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources in terms of increasing job satisfaction and improving employee performance.

4) The Role of Organizational Culture Variables

Organizational culture variable, based on regression analysis, proved to have a positive and significant relationship with job satisfaction (H5). This condition shows that the better the organizational culture of the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources will affect the job satisfaction of employees. Furthermore, if it is associated with employee performance, the results of the analysis show that there is a positive and significant relationship between organizational culture and employee performance (H10). This means that a good organizational culture will have an impact on improving employee performance in the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources.

Based on the description above, it can be interpreted that there is a role for organizational culture variables in this research model in the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources in terms of improving job satisfaction and employee performance.

CONCLUSIONS

- 1) The results of the study show that organizational commitment, competence, work motivation, organizational culture, job satisfaction and employee performance are descriptively well underway at the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources.
- 2) Organizational commitment does not have a significant effect on job satisfaction at the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources.
- 3) Competence has a significant effect on job satisfaction at the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources.
- 4) Work motivation does not have a significant effect on job satisfaction at the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources.
- 5) Organizational culture has a significant effect on job satisfaction in the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources.
- 6) Job satisfaction does not have a significant effect on the performance of Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources employees.
- 7) Organizational commitment has a significant effect on the performance of Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources employees.
- 8) Competence does not have a significant effect on the performance of Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources employees.
- 9) Work motivation does not have a significant effect on the performance of Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources employees.
- 10) Organizational culture has a significant effect on the performance of Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources employees
- 11) Indirectly organizational commitment does not have a significant effect on employee performance through job satisfaction at the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources.
- 12) Indirectly competence has a significant effect on employee performance through job satisfaction at the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources.
- 13) Indirectly work motivation does not have a significant effect on employee performance through job satisfaction at the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources.
- 14) Indirectly organizational culture has no significant effect on employee performance through job satisfaction at the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources.

SUGGESTION

- 1) The leadership of the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources needs to pay attention to organizational commitment and job satisfaction of employees because based on the statistical test the value of this variable is very low and of course this can reduce the performance of the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources itself.
- 2) From the results of the analysis of organizational commitment, it shows that employees of the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources are relatively low, this variable is very important because if this variable is low then employees will tend to not last long in the agency and of course switching institutions will be detrimental to the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources because will affect employee turnover rates.
- 3) Competence has very little influence on the performance of the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources employees, so that in the future the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources is expected to improve skills, analytical thinking, social roles, and encouragement to

achieve so that future competencies possessed by employees can increase and of course this will have an impact on improving the performance of the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources staff.

- 4) Work motivation has a very small influence on both job satisfaction and employee performance itself. In the future, more attention needs to be taken to increase the motivation of the work of the Aceh Department of Energy and Mineral Resources employees.
- 5) For future research, there can be more respondents using the object of research that is not from a government agency but private, so the results of the study will be more interesting.

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